

Research

Impact of Covid-19 On Education from the Aspect of Online Education, Hindrances to Public and Private Universities of Pakistan.

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Abstract: The ongoing pandemic, Covid-19 has influenced all nature of life on the globe, which no doubt has created a disastrous situation for all of the nations around the world. Where all sort of life is just stuck there a problem with educational attainment getting more severe loss and fatality. Access to quality education in developing countries is at risk, where educational technology is uneven and affordable. This study has diagnosis the ongoing issue of access to quality education in Pakistan during Covid-19 that how big population of the country is suffering from the problem of getting an education. The selected study has adopted the true-experimental quantitative research method to find the current situation of education in Public and Private universities. For this more than 400 teachers/faculty members and students of different public and private universities being participated in the study to find the fact about educational attainment during the pandemic. The study has to find drastic situations with online education, and suggesting emergency steps should be taken by government and academicians, civil society, and other humanitarian organizations.

This study aims to identify possible hindrances during online classes in academic institutions that are occurring during online classes at different public and private universities in Pakistan. as the government, policymakers should take the required measures to improve the quality and access of online education during the ongoing novel coronavirus, COVID-19

Keywords: Pandemic Covid-19, Higher Education, Education Attainment, Online Classes, Public, Private Universities, Pakistan Higher Education, HEC.

Introduction

The word COVID is driven from CO- Stands for Corona, VI- The Virus, and D- for the Disease (World Health Organization, 2020b). According to WHO, this virus is one newly discovered Disease/ infection, which is caused by a strain of coronavirus. Previously this is also known as 2019 novel coronavirus or it is also called 2019nCoV (World Health Organization, 2020a). Although the COVID-19 is a newly discovered virus that is linked to that same family of viruses which is the cause of some type of common cold and severe acute respiratory Syndrome (World Health Organization, 2020c).

The signs and symptoms depend upon the severity of cases but commonly that is documented by researchers (Peretto et al., 2020), (Yuen et al., 2020), (Child, 2020), (Mustafa, 2020), that patients who are suffering from COVID- 19 may develop a dry cough, with fever contain shortness of breath, but in more severe infection can cause difficulties to take a breath, and the patient may carry pneumonia. Although some studies (Yuan et al., 2020), (Deressa et al., 2020), have proved that rarely it can be fatal. These symptoms are very close to symptoms of flu (influenza) which is very common in developing countries as well as privileged areas(Ghimire et al., 2020), (Ghimire et al., 2019a), So the confirmation of COVID-19 has been made successful now.

This is proved from many research studies (Ren et al., 2020), (Kim, 2020), that this type of virus is transmitting through direct physical contacts through sneezing, coughing of that person who was already infected. It is also noted out that individuals can also be infected by touching surfaces contaminated with the viruses and touching their body parts like eyes, nose, and mouth (Aljahdali et al., 2020). The Coronavirus may survive on surfaces for several hours but it may kill through cleaning with soaps and other disinfectants (Bender, 2020) (Qiao, 2020), (Ghimire et al., 2019b).

Out Break of COVID-19 in Pakistan

The very first case was documented in Pakistan on dated February 26th, 2020 (Government of Pakistan, 2020), (Waris et al., 2020), since the federal government of Pakistan and the especially provincial government of Sindh in Pakistan take special measures and alleviation actions border abroad flights operations suspensions, as well as an academic institution from primary level to higher education level, was closed (Ali et al., 2020). Up to April 27th, 2020, there were 13,844 cases were documented, and from which 292 expiries were occurred due to novel COVID-19 reported from all over Pakistan (Government of Pakistan, 2020).

To control the rapid spread of COVID-19, the federal government of Pakistan forced shutdowns of public places, shops academic institutions (Ghimire et al., 2020), all the examinations were postponed and said to officials to take certain measure related to online classes for higher education institutions like colleges and universities (Government of Pakistan, 2020). And it was declared that reevaluation the situation government has continued the limitation regarding shutdown on 15th aril till May 10, 2020. According to WHO There was observed that due to implementing strong infection control measures and prevention the COVID-19 epidemic dissemination now it is under control in Pakistan compared to other developing countries (World Health Organization, 2020d). Till August 13, 2020, 286,613 cases confirmed all over Pakistan from which only 783 cases were critical, however number of diagnosed cases and mortality due to COVID-19 has crossed from the above figure in more than 100 developed and under developing countries around the globe including the USA, Spain, India, Italy, Bangladesh, etc.

Preventive Measures Taken by the Higher Education Commission (HEC) Pakistan

Early in the march 2020 outbreak of COVID-19 declared in Pakistan (Nadia Noree, Sarmad Wahaj Siddiqui, 2020), HEC announces suspension of classes in all institutes are engaged in higher education including private and public sector universities all over Pakistan (News, 2020), instead of this in march 2020 HEC issues general guidelines for all institutions/ universities in which some dissemination of basic practiced fixed for all students and faculty members to control the rapid transmission of viral infection, includes:

Awareness material is provided in all institutions (Pakistan, 2020) (International, 2020). visual alerts i.e. signs, posters at the entrance, and instructions on cough etiquette, hand, and respiratory

hygiene has been placed on the instruction of HEC Pakistan (The Higher Education Commission, 2020). Although staff/ employee who has mild symptoms of cough fever flu that relives from work and advised to avoid any physical contact.

During this outbreak help desk was provided in all institutes as well as HEC instructed all officials /leaders of institutions to provide daily situation report on COVID-19 and shared them on the university website to provide the latest information o students, faculty members, and staff. Beyond that all preventive measures implemented by HEC in all institutions/ universities in Pakistan that are engaged in higher education and awarding degrees (Pakistan, 2020) Implantation OF LMS in universities in Pakistan. The third vice-chancellors committee meeting called by the HEC chairman was held on April 23rd, 2020 in Islamabad Pakistan (News, 2020), with vice-chancellors of all universities, (including private and public sector) in which vice-chancellors (VCs) of all universities make a commitment to making online classes and develop e-learning management system in every university to control the education loss and situation created due to novel coronavirus.

During this third meeting, the university heads reviewed the progress and offer readiness to start online classes to avoid educational loss during the outbreak of COVID-19. The university heads expressed their efforts that they will take special measures with the collaboration of HEC they will fulfill needs regarding learning Management System (LMS) and contribute to the national efforts against the prevailing crisis. Instead of this, they asserted that they are committed to resolving all the expected issues which will face by the student's faculty members in implementing the LMS inside the institutions (Pakistan, 2020).

Beyond these efforts, higher Education Commission (HEC) Pakistan on June 2rd 2020 open a system to assure the students to solve their problems being faced by some of them, like internet connectivity issues, and quality lectures delivered through an online Learning Management System (LMS) (The Higher Education Commission, 2020), (Nafees & Khan, 2020).

Materials and methods

Methods

This study has been designed on a true experimental quantitative research method (Neil, 2011), (M.Gobanli, 1999), has been carried out in different public and private universities in Pakistan, through online participation of faculty members and undergraduate students of two major academic subjects including education, and Pharmacy. The study duration was three months in total, during the process study has matched with organizational as well as international protocols. The data collection strategy for the study has notified at the prior stage, the student's evaluation form and compiled data was distributed among the target population of the study who has given their feedback regarding hindrances of online classes during the ongoing pandemic COVID-19. Results are being measured in the result section after received feedback from the participants accordingly.

Study Design

for this study, a quantitative true experimental method (Neil, 2011), (M.Gobanli, 1999), has been adopted. In the prior stage, the hypothesis was generated, and an evaluation checklist was developed. In the second step, the checklist of hindrances sent to students and faculty members of different universities of Pakistan belong to southern Sindh Province. After one week of distribution, the responses were collected through email.

Figure 1. Detailed flow diagram of the study

Participants

Participants of the study are faculty members, teachers and students enrolled for online classes during ongoing pandemic Covid-19 in private and public sector universities of southern Sindh province of Pakistan majorly in the graduation course of Education and Pharmacy.

Measuring tools

In this study, three tools are used to measuring the data. A. Pre-assessment/ Hypothesis, B. Post-module evaluation survey, C.P post-assessment, includes students and faculty members of different universities

Data Collection

Data were collected from students and faculty members of different universities of Southern Sindh province of Pakistan, through one format. After collecting data and informed consents of participants the complete information including demographics and difficulties they are facing are evaluated and composed in results.

Data Analysis

Reliable baseline data with predictable variables have been distributed and collected through email among two categories of participants, one teacher/Faculty member, and the second students of two majors, B.Ed. & Pharm-D. Seven variables of hindrances in online class attainment during pandemic were set to measure the difficulty types/hindrances for online education in the public, private universities. All responses were collected accordingly and results are generated with responses of participants accordingly in the results section.

Results

Table 1: Teachers/Faculty Members & students Participated

Type of Participants	No. of Participants
Faculty Members	50
Students	400

Table 2: Participants from public and private universities

Type of university	Type of Participants	Total No. Of Participants
Private sector Universities	Faculty members	25
	Students	200
Public Sector universities	Faculty members	25
	Students	200

Table 3: Participants, Teachers/Faculty Members of Public & private universities

Category of faculty members	No. Of Participants
Professor	5+5
Assistant Professor	8+8
Lecturer	12+

(A). Students Participants from Phar-D Major

Table 4: Participants from Doctor of Pharmacy (Pharm-D) Major

Year of Study	No. Of Participants
1st Professional Pharm-D	50
2nd Professional Pharm-D	45
3rd Professional Pharm-D	40
4th Professional Pharm-D	35
5th Professional Pharm-D	30

(B). Year of Study in Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.)

Table 5: Participants of bachelor of Education (B.Ed.)

Year of Study	No. Of Participants
1st Professional B.Ed.	60
2nd Professional B.Ed.	50
3rd Professional B.Ed.	30
4th Professional B.Ed.	30
5th Professional B.Ed.	30

Type of Difficulty Faced by Faculty Members:

Figure 2 Measuring Hindrances Faced by Teachers/Faculty Members with Online Teaching in the Pandemic

Type of hindrances faced by students in online education attainment:

Figure 3 Measuring hindrances faced by students with online classes during Covid-19 pandemic

Findings

Fifty faculty members, teachers participated and reported to check the hindrance to access to online classes:

Study results have brought different severe kinds of hindrances in online classes in the country, have faced by teachers and faculty members. The major thing has found in the study process that the teachers have increased the amount of assignments 13, also in the exam measurement process, it has find teachers have lost their invigilation control for examination and assignment validity due to students malpractice during conducting online examination 50, internet speed and

connectivity issue 42, Electricity power Load-shedding 45, Technical problems in online classes portals, webs browsers, online classes applications (through which classes were conducted).38, Voice distortion.25, Portal hanging during online exam 22.

Four hundred students participated and reported a different kind of hindrances to access online classes:

A big number of students has faced such kinds of obstacles, like access and come up with the required level of participation in the academic process due to Connectivity, Electricity, website hanging, and voice distortion. The study has reported all issues within participants as under. Connectivity issue 273, Electricity Load-shedding 375, Technical Problems in Web-Portals, Webs, Apps 280, and Voice distortion 155. The reported population of students has echoed their voice about a big communication gap between teachers and them. Students reported that due to this gap in most of the classes they were unable to satisfactory answers for their primary questions 123, some rectified that online examination was different and difficult 100, portal hanging during online exams.50, Screen reading was dangerous for our eyesight but we were exposed to it so we had felt vision difficulties. 180, screen reading was bad enough to memorize many things 187. Further results are discussed in detail in results figures.

Discussion

During the study, all participants were involved in answering the questions about their current situations of online classes, which shows enthusiasm in the teachers/faculty members and students for getting online education in recently happening pandemic Covid-19. 400 teachers and students got involved and measured in the study, the results find are drastic and disastrous which is shows that during Covid-19 in higher educational institutions big population of the country's backbone is deprived of the basic right of education. After a long period of more than te months pandemic happened still government isn't come up with solid solutions. The efforts taken by HEC Pakistan are good initiatives but not enough to resolve the issue. The result section shows that a big communication gap between teachers and students, access to internet facilities, electricity availability, the unfamiliarity of web browsing are major issues which need main concern of the government education departments. The education system in Pakistan is lying

least effective system in the world (Nations, 2016), (Stelmach, 2018), which can be laid down if necessary action will not be taken on an emergency basis.

Conclusion

According to data results and finding, during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, every academic institution in Pakistan is facing multiple kinds of issues and problems with access to quality education and learning during the pandemic. Major reported issues with online classes are reported like, long-time electricity load-shedding problem, and the affordability of internet, computer, and other kinds of technical things which are necessary for online classes at the university level. So special consideration is needed in the education sector to make advancement for online classes at all levels of education, especially on the university level. The study concludes that in Pakistan education during a pandemic is at risk. Although steps taken by the federal government and provincial governments are not enough to resolve the issue. Major deficiency has found in the most recent educational policy of Pakistan (Government of Pakistan, 2018), that there is no any policy provision has made by the federal government on the prior level face or to encounter any emergencies about disasters, pandemic happen at any stage in the country. This means education in Pakistan is at risk at any time. Due to this reason, the SDGs 2030 and MDGs 2025 are at risk, which can create a big fall down in the country's economic and prosper social system. The study also has reviewed and studied steps taken by the federal and provincial governments for resolving issue, which has been found not satisfactory and below the needs. The findings of the study are shaking claims of the government about providing education during the pandemic and a clear voice against the disastrous situation of education within the country.

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Conflicts of Interest

There is no potential conflict of interest concerning the research authorship and publication of this study.

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